

Print: 3082-4060
Online: 3082-4079

PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

VOLUME 1

ISSUE 3 | JULY - SEPTEMBER ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

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PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue III | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

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“THE EVIDENTIARY VALUE OF POLYGRAPH RESULTS IN PHILIPPINE COURTS”

In the Philippine legal setting, the polygraph test’s scientific validity has been questioned. While it is widely used as an aid in investigations, its value in court remains limited. Polygraph results are not considered conclusive evidence and generally not admissible unless both parties stipulate and agree to its use. However, polygraph results evidentiary value is recognized in specific contexts.

The case of Porfirio Auxilio, Jr. v. NLRC, illustrates how polygraph results can be admitted in labor disputes. In this case, the Supreme Court gave weight to the polygraph results submitted by the employer to support its claim of loss of trust and confidence to his employee. The Court explained that in labor cases, substantial evidence suffices to establish party’s case. The polygraph results, while not conclusive evidence, contributed to support the employee’s dismissal.

In Philippine Savings Bank v. Hazel Thea F. Genove, the Supreme Court again emphasized that administrative and labor cases, the burden of proof do not require beyond reasonable doubt and can consider polygraph results alongside other corroborated evidence. The bank relied on polygraph examination to evaluate the veracity of its employees during investigations, and the Court did not reject polygraph results, provided there was substantial supporting evidence.

Contrastingly, in criminal cases like Cristeta Chua-Burce v. Court of Appeals and People v. Adoviso, the Supreme Court ruled that polygraph results are not admissible as evidence to determine guilt, as they do not meet the stringent requirement of proof beyond reasonable doubt. The Court cited the scientific uncertainty surrounding the accuracy of polygraph examinations.

In like manner, in People v. Amado Daniel and People v. Dioscoro Villamayor, polygraph results were not given weight in establishing criminal liability. The rulings consistently assert that guilt must be established based on solid evidence.

Moreover, in administrative cases, polygraph examinations have been used investigations to support disciplinary actions. The results were used in determining the termination or dismissal of the employees.

Finally, while polygraph results remain inadmissible in criminal cases as proof of guilt or innocence, Philippine jurisprudence recognizes their value in labor and administrative cases as long as they are corroborated by

other evidence, they can support findings of fact under the more lenient standard of substantial evidence which plays a crucial role in resolving disputes where moral certainty is not required.

